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Introduction

The BRIDGE project aims to enhance the Kyiv School of Economics' innovation capacity, focusing on research management and research-to-policy transfer on participatory and deliberative democracy. The project will support Ukrainian hromadas (communities) in participatory decision-making to reconstruct housing and infrastructures destroyed by the Russian war against Ukraine by implementing the pilot citizens' assembly knowledge and related skills to a real-life case of a selected hromada.

In so doing, BRIDGE addresses gaps in public administration by exploring the integration of representative and participatory democracy during crises, specifically by conducting a pilot citizens' assembly around a recovery project on the local level and the study of the utilization of digital participatory tools, including an e-Idea module, for recovery planning. BRIDGE will also set up a multi-level policy lab to ensure knowledge circulation between research and practice within Ukraine and between Ukraine and its EU partners.

The communication and dissemination plan is based on a strategy to increase the visibility of the project and to ensure the outputs reach the main target groups, resulting in its impact on the area of implementation.

The project will be implemented by a consortium of partners representing international organizations. All the organizations are considered project ambassadors and will be involved in communication and dissemination activities to varying degrees.

This document aims to start communication activities by providing first guidelines. The communication and dissemination plan is expected to be supplemented by additional information during the implementation of the project when further decisions are made regarding communication activities.

The dissemination, exploitation, and communication plan includes the following parts:

- Communication and dissemination objectives
- Visual identity
- Compliance with contractual obligations
- Key target audiences
- Key messages
- Communication and dissemination channels and instruments
- Timing
- KPIs and Monitoring of the Project

1. Dissemination

1.1 Communication and Dissemination Objectives and Tasks

The overarching communication and dissemination **objective** of the project is to enhance the visibility of the Kyiv School of Economics (KSE), inside and outside Ukraine, and to ensure that project results, including from research in deliberative and digital democracy, are disseminated to relevant stakeholders.

Specific communication and dissemination objectives of the project are the following:

- 1) To set up infrastructure for effective project dissemination and communication and increase the international visibility of KSE
- 2) To raise the attractiveness of KSE as a mobility destination for talents
- 3) To support the research-to-policy transfer by disseminating the project results to national and local governments and governmental agencies in Ukraine, thus creating a community of practice for digital and participatory democracy.
- 4) To raise awareness of project topics among the general public

To achieve these goals, the following broad tasks are set in the WP5:

T5.1 Implementing the Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) and increasing KSE visibility among Ukrainian and international stakeholders in the field of democracy, digital participation, and deliberation.

T5.2 Increased the attractiveness of KSE to talented students and PhD candidates via organizing KSE professors' guest lectures in partner universities and holding online guest lectures for KSE students by professors from partner universities.

T5.3 Communication to the general public.

T5.4 Final project conference.

1.2 Target Audiences and Dissemination Channels

The following target audiences are regarded as relevant to the project:

- KSE researches, research management and teaching staff
- National and local governments, governmental agencies; policymakers in Ukraine and the EU
- International scientific community (in the field of digital and participatory democracy) and Ukrainian scientific community

- Ukrainian civil society in the part of recovery/civic participation
- KSE students
- International (PhD) students
- Ukrainian and international general public

During the strategic session held at the kick-off meeting in Berlin on 30.10-01.11.2024, a map of these stakeholders was developed and subsequently revised for this plan, based on two criteria (Figure 1):

- 1) Interest: To what extent is a stakeholder interested in the project and/or digital or participatory democracy more generally?
- 2) Influence: To what extent does a stakeholder's (non-)cooperation affect the project's objectives and/or the digital and participatory democracy development in Ukraine or abroad more generally?

Based on the interest/influence matrix, **four strategic communication groups** of target audiences were identified. The Consortium realizes that stakeholder groups are not homogenous, meaning there can be different depths of communication with individuals and organizations from the same target audience, depending on mutual interest and capacity. Nevertheless, we set one priority for each group to optimize messaging and resource allocation. A database with stakeholders' contact information and other details will be stored on the Project's Drive.

Figure 1. Stakeholder map with priority action

Communication priority 1: Manage closely (key stakeholders that affect project's objectives and overall mission and are interested in it)

Target audience 1.1 a) KSE researches, teaching and b) admin (research management) staff

Messages: a) KSE, through cooperation with top European universities in their fields, provides KSE researchers and teaching staff with a unique opportunity to increase their capacity to research and teach at the intersection of cutting-edge decision-support technologies (open data, machine learning, digital applications), participatory democracy, and public administration. b) KSE, through cooperation with top European partners, is a university that uses leading research management methods, and provides unique learning and practical opportunities through managing EU-funded and other large research projects.

Dissemination activities:

- involve in train-the-trainer events and hackathon (targeted invitations, explanations of advantages, seeking feedback on program)
- provide public communication support for participants who hold public lectures after capacity building;
- dissemination of stories and activities done by participants in capacity building; co-organize events such as hackathon and policy labs
- KSE screens

Target audience 1.2 Local self-government authorities (LSG) and their associations in Ukraine

Messages: Digital and deliberative approaches can help local governments meaningfully involve citizens in recovery-related decision-making. KSE, through its cooperation with top European universities in participatory and digital democracy, is an impartial go-to university partner in Ukraine for tested and practically applicable solutions and guidelines on how to do it.

Dissemination activities:

- Information campaign for an open selection process to host citizens' assembly in Kyiv, Zhytomyr and Chernihiv regions, project website updates, invitation to policy labs
- For LSGs of hromadas with pilot citizens' assembly and research sites: regular meetings, featuring on BRIDGE website and social media, linkage to Ukrainian media (see section 1.4.5), providing access to Ukrainian/international policy conference online (offline, subject to obtaining separate funding), inviting to final conference and speaking invitations to participate in urban events by KSE
- 15 hromadas will be selected to observe citizens' assembly in the making

Communication priority 2: Raise interest (stakeholders that either affect project's KPIs or democratic practices but are not interested in the project per se)

Target audience 2.1 The government and parliament, governmental agencies of Ukraine, including but not limited to the Ministry of Education, Cabinet of Ministers (CMU) Secretariat, relevant

Parliamentary committee, the Ministry for Development of Communities and Territories of Ukraine, Ministry for Digital Transformation, Regional Military Administrations (Regional Development Agencies).

Messages: Community (digital) participation and deliberation, specifically, can provide a constructive and democratic way for recovery planning with residents. KSE, through cooperation with top European universities in participatory and digital democracy, is an impartial go-to university partner for tested and practically applicable solutions and guidelines for community (digital) participation and deliberation.

Dissemination activities:

- KSE approved as a strategic partner for CMU for the implementation of the state civil society strategy development of Ukraine, in the topic of deliberative democracy
- Policy lab invitations
- E-mail updates, project event invitations, joining public consultations initiated by relevant stakeholders

Target audience 2.2 International policy community including but not limited to development NGOs, Governmental development agencies, Congress of Local and Regional Authorities of the Council of Europe, DG Near, REA, Democracy NGOs, Municipal partnership facilitators, Foreign local authorities

Messages: Ukraine, in general, and our consortium, in particular, possess unique case study data and findings on citizen e-participation and deliberation in shaping local and national policies during wartime that will help international policy actors design more inclusive and effective participatory interventions not just in Ukraine, but also elsewhere.

Dissemination activities:

- information emails, website and social media updates (section 1.4., 1.4.2, 1.4.4)
- proactive applications to policy conferences as speakers and attendees,
- publications in the EU popular science (digital) democracy outlets
- invitation as speakers to consortium events, where applicable and appropriate (policy labs, final event, consortium meetings)

Target audience 2.3 International (PhD) students (primary focus: partner universities)

Messages: Ukraine, in general, and KSE, in particular, is a mobility destination for talents (even if only virtual is possible now).

- mutual guest lectures between KSE and partners (at least one per university)
- disseminate hybrid hackathon invitations
- academic publications (see section 1.4.3)
- academic conference presentations (see section 1.4.3)

Communication priority 3: Connect (stakeholders that have high interest in deliberative and digital participatory practices but their (non-) involvement does not influence project KPIs and mission significantly)

Target audience 3.1 International scientific community (in the field of digital and participatory democracy), including Advisory Board members, democracy labs, similar research projects

Messages: Ukraine, in general, and our consortium, in particular, possess unique case study data and findings on citizen e-participation and deliberation in shaping local and national policies during wartime that links academic research and policymaking and reinterprets classical theories of public administration, social mobilization, digital and participatory democracy.

KSE is a strong research university making it a top mobility destination for talents, as well as partner in research.

Dissemination activities:

- academic conference participation (see section 1.4.3),
- academic publications and published data (see section 1.4.3)
- open access publication of relevant project deliverables (e.g. on project website, Zenodo)
- methodological exchange, peer review (upon mutual consent)
- communicate cooperation opportunities in new research projects,
- propose dedicated sections at top thematic conferences or workshops,

Target audience 3.2 Ukrainian civil society in the part of recovery/civic participation

Messages: KSE, through cooperation with top European universities in participatory and digital democracy, is an impartial go-to university partner for tested and practically applicable solutions and guidelines on how to involve citizens in optimizing the reconstruction efforts, using digital and deliberative approaches.

Dissemination activities:

- policy lab invitations,
- seek one-on-one thematic consultations
- e-mail updates,
- project event invitations,
- experience sharing at their events (on request)

Communication priority 4: Keep informed (stakeholders that have low interest in deliberative and digital participatory practices and their (non-) involvement does not influence project KPIs and mission significantly)

Target audience 4.1 Ukrainian scientific community

Messages: KSE is a collaborative research partner and facilitator of international knowledge transfer in the field of digital and deliberative democracy between Ukraine and the international scientific community.

Dissemination activities:

- presentation at thematic events in Ukraine,

- website and social media (section 1.4.1 and 1.4.2),
- inclusion to the annual newsletter; targeted invitations to newsletter subscription;
- extend invitations to Alliance of Ukrainian Universities' staff to attend publicly open activities done by KSE participants to the capacity building.

Target audience 4.2 a) General public, among them, b) business (construction & architects) in Ukraine, c) general public abroad

Messages: Community participation and deliberation, specifically, can provide a constructive and socially responsible way for designing (re)construction projects. **a, b)** KSE is an impartial go-to partner for implementing these solutions. **c)** Ukraine is a vivid example.

- press-releases to media (see section 1.4.5),
- press conference in a citizens' assembly municipality,
- publications in the Ukrainian and EU popular science (digital) democracy outlets,
- social media and website updates (section 1.4.1 and 1.4.2)
- coordinate with KSE business school corporate social responsibility events

Target audience 4.3 KSE students

Messages: Digital and deliberative approaches can help local governments to meaningfully involve citizens in recovery-related decision-making. BRIDGE is a great opportunity to understand how this works and contribute.

Dissemination activities:

- open guest lectures online and offline
- social media updates (section 1.4.2)
- KSE screens

1.3 Visual Identity

A recognizable project identity, that reflects the main project concept, was created. In particular, the project logo (Figure 2) and project logobook was created and stored on the Project Drive.

Figure 2. Project logo

LOGOTYPE: HOW TO USE IT		
	MAIN LOGOTYPE	SECOND OPTION
<p>POSITIVE LOGOTYPE VERSION Used on light backgrounds</p>		
<p>NEGATIVE LOGOTYPE VERSION Used on dark backgrounds</p>		
<p>BLACK & WHITE LOGOTYPE Please use these logotypes when the main logotype cannot be used due to legal or printing limitations.</p>		

Figure 3. Project Logobook page

The templates for social media accounts (Figure 4 and Figure 5) have been designed.

Figure 4. LinkedIn template

Figure 5. Facebook templates

1.3.1 Compliance with Contractual Obligations

According to Grant Agreement regulation, the following approach should be implemented:

Unless otherwise agreed with the granting authority, communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (translated into local languages, where appropriate):

Funded by the
European Union

Co-funded by the
European Union

The emblem must remain distinct and separate and cannot be modified by adding other visual marks, brands or text. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support.

When displayed in association with other logos (e.g. of beneficiaries or sponsors), the emblem must be displayed at least as prominently and visibly as the other logos.

For the purposes of their obligations under this Article, the beneficiaries may use the emblem without first obtaining approval from the granting authority. This does not, however, give them the right to exclusive use. Moreover, they may not appropriate the emblem or any similar trademark or logo, either by registration or by any other means.

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate):

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Ukrainian language version:

Фінансується Європейським Союзом. Однак висловлені погляди та думки є лише думками автора і не обов'язково відображають позицію Європейського Союзу чи Європейського агентства з досліджень. Ані Європейський Союз, ані грантодавець не можуть нести за них відповідальності.

1.4 Communication and Dissemination Channels and Instruments

This section specifies some key communication channels, briefly listed according to communication priorities and target audiences in Section 1.3.

1.4.1 Project Website

A user-friendly project website (<https://bridge.kse.ua/>), which includes detailed information about the project is at the final stage of development at the moment of composing this document. The website will be the main information resource of the project and its main purpose is to increase the visibility of the project's aims and outputs to all target audiences and wider public. The content will be posted in two languages (Ukrainian and English).

The project website contains:

- details on project aims & objectives
- an interactive block that will reveal in more detail the main concepts and terms within the project (in the format of key guiding questions and answers to them in pop-up windows)
- information about project partners including links to the partners' websites
- information about the project team
- information about the Advisory Board
- news
- upcoming events and project activities
- project materials
- contact details
- social media links/buttons
- acknowledgement of the EU support and the European flag (emblem), and a project disclaimer

The website will be continuously updated with information about all project activities and outputs. Partners' websites will be used in disseminating information about the project as well. An example of the website's main page and its sections can be found in Figures 6 and 7.

More detailed description of the BRIDGE project website can be found in the respective Deliverable «D5.2. Project Page».

Figure 6. Project website: main page

About the Project

The BRIDGE project aims to enhance the innovative potential of the Kyiv School of Economics, focusing on research management and the transfer of research outcomes into policy in the areas of participatory and deliberative democracy. The project supports Ukrainian communities in participatory decision-making related to the restoration of housing and infrastructure destroyed as a result of Russia's war against Ukraine.

In so doing, BRIDGE addresses gaps in public administration by exploring the integration of representative and participatory democracy during crises, specifically by conducting a pilot citizens' assembly around a recovery project on the local level and the study of the utilization of digital participatory tools, including an e-idea module, for recovery planning. The BRIDGE project will also set up a multi-level policy lab to ensure knowledge circulation between research and practice within Ukraine and between Ukraine and its EU partners.

Duration:
2024 - 2027

Budget:
€1.5 million

Coordinator:
Kyiv School of Economics (Ukraine)

Partners:
Erasmus University Rotterdam (Netherlands)
Technical University of Berlin (Germany)
University of Tartu (Estonia)

Associated Partner:
Center for Innovations Development (Ukraine)

Show less

Partners

Contacts

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[f](#) [in](#) [@](#)

Feedback Form

Fill in the details so we can contact you

Your Name*
Name

Email*
example@example.com

Phone
+XX XXX XXX XXX XX

Message*
Enter your question

I use podor

Submit

About the project
Our Team
Advisory board

Materials
News

Events
Contact information

Socials
[f](#) [in](#) [@](#)

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Figure 7. Project website: About the Project, Partners and Contact sections on the main page

1.4.2 Social media

The project website is linked to [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [Instagram](#) accounts to engage the primary target audiences using organic reach and targeted advertising where necessary. Social media will be used to share project messages and redirect users towards the website. Personal pages of opinion leaders in the project field and representatives of partner institutions will be involved in promoting information about the project. Existing social media groups will be used to disseminate information, such as “Spilnota partysypatoriv” (Community of participators), Digital Democracy, and Open Government (curated by Consortium member Dmytro Khutkyy) and similar.

Partners' LinkedIn, Facebook, and Instagram accounts will be used when relevant, including individual accounts of project researchers and organizations (including Erasmus University Rotterdam, Kyiv School of Economics, Technische Universität Berlin, Political Science - University of Tartu, Center for Innovations Development, ERA Chair in e-Governance and Digital Public Services) and groups (e.g., Digital Democracy and Open Government, Civic Technology and Open Government - Global, Social Media & Digital Technology For Development, e-Democracy in Ukraine, e-Democracy and Open Data in Ukraine, eServices in Ukraine).

1.4.3 Academic publications and conferences

Project Partners are planning to publish within the project at least six academic articles (single- and co-authored) in high-impact Q1/Q2 scientific journals, open access, in political science, public administration, and digital governance, such as Governance, Democratization, Policy&Society, Political Science and Politics, British Journal of Political Science, International Political Science Review, Political Studies Review, Government Information Quarterly, Internet Policy Review, Information Society, Policy & Internet, Digital Government: Research and Practice, Information Polity, Transforming Government: People, Process, Policy.

The Project will contribute to international academic conferences. KSE will lead the consortium's section and paper proposals on digital governance, democracy, and (post-)crises reconstruction to general and digital-government-focused academic conventions, such as: the European Consortium for Political Research (ECPR) General Conference and Joint Sessions, Eastern European International Studies Association Annual Conference, Annual Tartu Conference, International Conference on Theory and Practice of Electronic Governance (ICEGOV), American Political Science Association (APSA) Annual Meeting, the COST-Action "Intergovernmental Coordination from Local to European Governance (IGCOORD)" Annual Meeting, International Political Science Association (IPSA), Annual International Conference on Digital Government Research (DGO), Digital Government Conference (DGO), Electronic Government, Electronic Participation, and the Conference for E-Democracy and Open Government Conference (EGOV-CeDEM-ePart), Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS). Project activities will also be carried out during working meetings with partners in scientific projects and networks such as the Digital Democracy consortium, MULTISSET consortium, HROMADA network, etc.

1.4.4 Policy publications and events in Ukraine and the EU

Through collaborative policy publications and panel speaker invitations, advanced partners will facilitate KSE's outreach to international policy actors and brokers engaged in the field of Ukraine's reconstruction and/or digital governance, such as the Brussels-based European Digital Development Alliance (EDDA) and the European Citizen Action Service (ECAS, Brussels), Eastern Partnership Civil Society Forum (EaP CSF), Council of Europe (CoE) European Committee on

Democracy and Governance (CDDG), Digital Society Initiative (DSI, Zurich University), Open Government Partnership (OGP), and Ukraine Democracy Initiative (UDI, Australia).

Our Team plans to submit the articles to leading EU popular science (digital) democracy outlets such as OpenDemocracy, Eurozine, Wired, EUIdeas, The Conversation, ECPR blog, The Loop, and EDD.

In Ukraine, the project team will organize a high-profile **final event** to disseminate project results to target audiences. The event will occur in a hybrid format in Kyiv or, considering security considerations, a panel at the Annual Tartu Conference. The project results will be presented with a particular focus on the pilot research and the way forward in the field. The conference will bring together top-level researchers, students, stakeholders, and public administrators and include sessions for the general public. Additionally, KSE will present at thematic conferences of other organizers, such as Lviv Urban Forum, Forum for Participatory Urbanism, and municipal fora.

1.4.5 Media Relations in Ukraine and the EU

The communication strategy involves different forms of cooperation with **international and Ukrainian media** to maximize the dissemination of information about the project and its results to the general public. Partners will coordinate press releases to disseminate project events, achieved milestones, and important research results on national and EU levels.

Cooperation with Ukrainian media will take place at both national and local levels and will include establishing cooperation with such resources as:

- top national online media (Liga.Net, Ukrainska Pravda, NV, Ukrainskyi Tyzhden, Suspilne, Lb.ua), information agencies (Ukrinform and UNN), Hromadske radio, as well as Eu4ukraine Review at the online platform eu4ukraine.eu
- specialized online resources (VoxUkraine, decentralization.ua, Vikno vidnovlennya)
- audio podcast (YODA PODCAST) and YouTube podcast (Vidbudova Podcast by VoxUkraine)
- online portals for Ukrainian NGOs (prostir.ua and gurt.org.ua)
- regional media conference in the community where the pilot citizens' assembly will be held

Cooperation with media involves various formats of materials (announcements and press releases, analytical articles, podcasts, interviews, and radio broadcasts).

Media representatives will also be invited to the final conference, where the project results will be presented.

1.4.6 Email and print

Direct email is considered one of the relevant channels for reaching our target audiences. A mailing list will be created to disseminate information about the project to the representatives of the international scientific community in the field of digital democracy (e.g., the University of Tartu Skytte Institute of Political Studies, European Digital Development Alliance, Digital Government Society, Digital Sociology working group of the International Sociological Association). A newsletter will be distributed annually to highlight projects' achievements and overall accomplishments in the field. The second mailing list will be created for key Ukrainian stakeholders, including RISE Ukraine - Coalition for Reconstruction, Reanimation Package of Reforms, eDem working group, etc.

A **newsletter** will be distributed annually to highlight projects' achievements and overall accomplishments in the field to the relevant audiences, as mentioned in section 1.3.

Printed promotional and training materials will be developed for each of the main project events, such as leaflets explaining the main project concepts and instruments or brochures with project objectives and outcomes.

A project banner will be developed to contain the project and partners' logos, a description of the main project concepts, and a QR code that will redirect visitors to the project website and social media accounts.

2. Exploitation

Translating research and capacity-building results into practice is at the core of this project as we aim to improve KSE's ability to not just communicate to stakeholders, but to engage them in research to ensure the most relevant research outputs. Therefore:

1. KSE will collaborate closely with policy-makers at various levels, including regional and local authorities, via **policy labs (WP1)** to co-create relevant (research) outputs. Additionally, research results presentations will be sought to be conducted to key stakeholders from Ukrainian public authorities such as The Ministry for Communities and Territories Development of Ukraine (MinRegion), the DREAM project office, The Ministry of Digital Transformation of Ukraine (MinDigital), The Secretariat of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine.
2. KSE will also develop decision-support tools for solving various real-life problems based on data. Specifically, through a **hybrid two-day hackathon (WP1)** at the KSE, organized with UTARTU and TU Berlin, where KSE researchers and students and Associate Partner CID will present and share their experiences with developing decision support and digital democratic innovations based on Ukrainian open data sets.
3. KSE will provide **training to the participants** (researchers, managers, and students) of the Alliance of Ukrainian Universities on various cross-cutting topics in EU projects, such as ethics, GDPR, Open Science, and FAIR principles (e.g., data archiving for its long-term preservation), and gender dimension, based on two trainings for trainers (ToTs) from partners (WP1).
4. A **workshop on deliberative opportunities will be held (WP1)**. The **"Spring School on Public Deliberation: Introductory Course into Citizens' Assemblies"** (Kyiv, April 2025) will reveal the

opportunities for participatory decision-making for rebuilding housing and infrastructures destroyed by the Russian war against Ukraine. The facilitators from Ukrainian local civic activists and professionals will be trained to form a pool of facilitators for the WP3 pilot citizens' assembly.

- Information events for Ukrainian hromadas of Kyiv, Zhytomyr, and Chernihiv regions called "Deliberation: new democratic instruments for a cohesive hromada" will be held in April 2025 (WP3).** These events will be dedicated to instruments of deliberative and participatory democracy and the benefits for hromadas in participatory decision-making for the reconstruction of housing and infrastructures destroyed by the Russian war against Ukraine. After that, the selection process for hromadas will start. A pilot citizens' assembly will be held in one selected hromada to resolve a relevant issue.

3. Timing

Communication and dissemination activity will be provided from the start until the end of the project, emphasizing important dates and events within the project, e.g. pilot citizens' assembly, hybrid hackathon, and final conference with presentation of the research.

A detailed Communication and Dissemination Plan is developed and stored in the Project's Drive. It is a living document that will be constantly filled with communication and dissemination activities relevant to the stages of project implementation.

4. KPIs and Monitoring of the Project

According to the approved Grant Proposal of the BRIDGE Project, Communication and Dissemination strategy KPIs were set:

Quarterly monitored indicators			
Project website	- the numbers of project page views	a total of over 500	number of page visits to the website, bounce rate and average duration of visits, number of references to project on search engines
	- publication downloads	a total of over 200	
Social media accounts	- social media reactions	a total of over 500	number of posts, number of clicks/likes/shares/comments, number of

	- comments	a total of over 100	mentions/profile visits/active followers, traffic data
	- reposts	a total of over 25	
Annually monitored indicators			
General	- the number of replies to emails	over 25	number of mailing list members, number of press releases, number of offline event participants
	- annual number of press releases	1 per country	
Whole project period indicators			
General	- academic articles (single- and co-authored) published in high-impact Q1/Q2 journals	6	
KSE Institutional KPIs	- amount of funding, mobilized through European research support schemes (e.g., HORIZON)	1 mln EUR	
	- no. of citations in social sciences (excluding economics)	900	
	- no. of publications in peer-reviewed, high-impact journals by the Social sciences & humanities department	13	
	- no. of policy interventions co-created with policy stakeholders from idea to implementation	3	